

Harnessing Electric Fields at the Air-Water Interface: The Case of Soap Films

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Abstract: Interfacial electric-fields have since long been implicated in chemical reactivity, assuming particular relevance in, for instance, natural enzymatic systems or for key reactions influencing atmospheric chemistry. Reports documenting fantastic rate enhancement at the interface in artificial systems are also extant, though direct mechanistic insight into how the interfacial electric field plays a role is lacking. In this perspective, we use soap films as model systems and test for the impact of the interfacial electric field on rates of bimolecular electron transfer, using time-resolved fluorescence spectroscopy. Surprisingly, a substantial acceleration in rates is not seen. We encapsulate lessons learned from both experiment and theory, and highlight potentially overlooked parameters and challenges vis-à-vis harnessing the interfacial field in particular – and the interface generally – for affecting useful chemistry. Indeed, attribution of remarkable reactivity at the interface to the asymmetric electric field must be treated with due caution.

Introduction

The central role played by electrostatics in chemical reactivity is well-known, specifically in the context of enzymatic catalysis, where, for example, local electric fields experienced by substrates on binding sites can help lower the energy of the transition state, thus leading to accelerated reaction rates and yields^{1,2}. Consequently, work on chemical reactivity in synthetic systems has sought to tap into favourable properties of the (air-water) interface, where the intrinsic asymmetry can lead to distinct pH, solvation, reactant concentrations and electric fields compared to the bulk, thus benefitting reactivity^{3,4}. In this context, the last two decades have seen considerable research into microdroplets⁵ – both as miniature reactors for organic synthesis (catalysis “on water”) with dramatically accelerated rates^{6,7}, but also as models for chemistry in the atmosphere^{8,9}.

Although reports of enhanced rates are many, direct kinetic measurements are few, with most relying on detected products and yields using mass spectrometry. The first direct measurement of rate acceleration at the air-water interface was reported by Tahara and co-workers in 2021 using femtosecond time-resolved sum-frequency generation (TR-SFG) for measuring the rate of phenol oxidation¹⁰. The measured rate constant was four orders of magnitude larger compared to the same reaction in bulk solution (100 fs to 5 ns). The origins of the observed reactivity are unclear, but the strong interfacial electric field of ca. 1 V/nm is oftentimes implicated; as recently as this year, however, such claims have been put under scrutiny^{11,12}.

In this study, we use soap films to test for the impact of the air-water interface on bimolecular electron transfer, by using time-resolved fluorescence spectroscopy. The system can be thought to be a relatively pristine platform for direct probing of the unperturbed air-water interface compared to, e.g. generation of electrosprays. Further, time-resolved fluorescence measurements should yield direct kinetic insight into rate enhancement, rather than indirect monitoring via product yields. Therefore, the results obtained herein can be expected to weigh in on a plethora of findings and emergent questions in the literature at large.

The molecular structures of the chosen surfactant dyes for the study can be seen in Figure 1, which include a newly synthesized charge-transfer dye ("CT dye") and amphiphilic versions of Rhodamine, Fluorescein, and Pyrene. Methylviologen (MV^{2+}) and Sodium Iodide (I^-) were employed as quenchers. Different base surfactants, hexaethylene glycol monododecyl ether ($C_{12}E_6$, neutral charge) and sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS, negatively charged) were used to make the soap films: as we shall elucidate, ab-initio calculations indicate that the strong electric field at the interface persists despite addition of both these surfactants (or salts) and can be expected to vary by not more than a factor of 2–3. In the interest of brevity, representative results obtained for Rhodamine and Pyrene are discussed in detail in the following sections, while other trials are presented in the supporting information.

Figure 1. Molecular structures of the surfactant dyes chosen for the fluorescence quenching studies.

Results and Discussion

Quenching of Rhodamine by Iodide and MV^{2+}

Time-correlated single photon counting (TCSPC) traces of Rhodamine quenching by Iodide and MV^{2+} are presented in figures 2 and 3, respectively, with $C_{12}E_6$ used as base surfactant in the former and SDS in the latter. Four cases are compared: i) the dye in a soap film made from 1 CMC of the base surfactant ($C_{12}E_6$), i.e. a measurement sensitive to the interface (Figures 2c and 3c); ii) a bulk measurement with the same solutions used to make the soap films but measured in a standard 1x1 cm cuvette with right-angle detection geometry (Figures 2a and 3a); iii) a bulk measurement of the dye in 10 CMC of the base surfactant, i.e. when it can be expected to be confined in micelles of the base surfactant; and, finally, iv) non-alkylated version of the dye in water, i.e. a bulk measurement with no surfactants present.

While there are minor differences between the cases (as can be seen in the corresponding Stern-Volmer plots seen in figure 4), ultimately no drastic rate increase is observed at the soap film interface. One possibility is that the Iodide quenching mechanism is not electron-transfer and rather due to the heavy-atom effect which may be relatively insensitive to the electric field at the interface. Nevertheless, diffusional encounter of the charged iodide with the dye at the interface should still be strongly affected by an electric field.

Further, the observed trend is similar for the case of quenching by MV^{2+} where electron transfer is the only viable mechanism and the quencher is cationic with an anionic base surfactant. Surprisingly, no differences are observed between the soap film and the same solution used to make it measured in the bulk phase at 1 CMC of the base surfactant. This strongly suggest that there is no significant effect of an interfacial electric field in the soap film.

While it may be tempting to consider the lack of dynamic quenching observed upon using 10 CMC of the base surfactant and the non-alkylated dye as notable differences, they can be suitably rationalized by keeping in mind the largely static quenching mechanism (see SI). At 10 CMC, there is greater probability of the quencher binding to micelles with no dye present; in the absence of surfactants, a diffusional encounter is improbable at the low concentrations tested given the short lifetime (few nanoseconds) of the dye, thereby explaining the observations.

Figure 2. Top panel: Quenching of 10 μ M Rhodamine by NaI in bulk solutions of $C_{12}E_6$ at a) 1 CMC and b) 10 CMC. Bottom panel: Quenching of c) 10 μ M Rhodamine by NaI in a soap film made of 1 CMC $C_{12}E_6$, and d) of 10 μ M non-alkylated Rhodamine by NaI in bulk solution with no surfactants present. Quencher concentrations as indicated in the legend. Excitation wavelength = 470 nm, monitoring wavelength = 590 nm (Rhodamine emission maximum). Quenching in soap film / bulk (1 CMC) is larger by around a factor of 3 compared to 10 CMC, however, no substantial difference between the bulk and interfacial 1 CMC measurements is seen.

Figure 3. Top panel: Quenching of 10 μM Rhodamine by MV^{2+} in bulk solutions of SDS at a) 1 CMC and b) 10 CMC. Bottom panel: Quenching of c) 10 μM Rhodamine by MV^{2+} in a soap film made of 1 CMC SDS, and d) of 10 μM non-alkylated Rhodamine by MV^{2+} in bulk solution with no surfactants present. Quencher concentrations as indicated in the legend. Excitation wavelength = 470 nm, monitoring wavelength = 590 nm (Rhodamine emission maximum). Quenching in soap film / bulk (1 CMC) is larger by around a factor of 20 compared to 10 CMC, however this can be attributed to a trivial electrostatic effect: there should be a greater probability of the positively charged quencher preferentially binding to SDS micelles with no dye present at 10 CMC. The notion is supported by the primarily static quenching mechanism (see Figures S2–S4 in the SI).

Figure 4. Stern-Volmer plots for the quenching of Rhodamine by MV^{2+} (left) and Iodide (right).

Quenching of Pyrene by Iodide and MV^{2+}

One potential cause of the lack of any substantial rate enhancement at the interface could be due to the positioning of the dye headgroup *vis-à-vis* the mean maximum of the interfacial electric field – inasmuch as it can be considered a predominant factor when assessing charge transfer reactivity. While the interfacial field has a depth of ca. 30 Å, its strength everywhere is not the same. Given the headgroup size – with a radius of around 7 Å – the extent of solvation and impact of the electric field, and any resulting rate enhancement of the electron transfer reaction, may be thought to be fairly sensitive to its position. Consequently, we chose to test amphiphilic Pyrene, which possesses a smaller, flatter headgroup, and is also liable to be far more hydrophobic due to the lack of charge – unlike Rhodamine or Fluorescein – thus, potentially, having a more optimal position at the interface.

As can be seen in figure 5 which summarizes the results, no remarkable rate differences are observed among the four cases tested even for amphiphilic Pyrene, mirroring the situation described above. For Iodide, the observed quenching is 55% in 1 CMC bulk solution, 50% in soap films, 25% in 10 CMC bulk solution, and 52% in the non-amphiphilic version of the dye tested without any surfactants present. Likewise, for MV²⁺ 26% quenching is observed in bulk (1 CMC), 32% in bulk (10 CMC), 30% in soap films (1 CMC), and 75% in the non-alkylated dye. A potential explanation for the larger rate in the non-alkylated counterpart is the greater possibility of favorable associative interaction between the dye and quencher phenyl groups. Qualitatively, the results were similar for the other dyes and quenchers tested, and taken as a whole do not reveal any remarkable interfacial effects, at least when soap films are used as a platform.

Figure 5. Summary of percentage dynamic quenching of pyrene by Iodide and MV²⁺ (concentrations of 12.5 and 25 mM, respectively). Pyrene concentration = 2 μM, unquenched lifetime for surfactant pyrene = 27 ns. Excitation wavelength = 340 nm, monitoring wavelength = 380 nm (Pyrene monomer emission maximum).

Outlook

The presented results stand in stark contrast to naïve expectations from the literature, and thus prompt due reflection. One notable difference between this study and previous reports which document acceleration is that the amphiphilic molecules considered here are far larger, and consequently more likely to be solvated, or not optimally positioned near the interface. Even if that is assumed to be the case, the breadth of data is nevertheless indicative of the fact that harnessing the interfacial electric field for bimolecular reactivity is non-trivial. Quenching in many cases investigated here appears to be close to diffusion controlled for neutral reactants ($k \approx 1 \cdot 10^{10} \text{ M}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$), which could be thought to explain the absence of further rate increase at the interface. In some cases, however, it is far from that limit (e.g. Figure 5). Moreover, an electric field would be expected to favor diffusional encounter with quenchers of the right charge and reach much higher values. Therefore, we do not believe our results can be explained by being in the diffusion-controlled limit.

One may of course question the sensitivity of the technique employed to the interface specifically: unlike fluorescence, TR-SFG selectively probes the surface. Although it is true that fluorescence is collected indiscriminately from both the surface and the bulk of the soap film, the employed conditions preclude a substantial signature from the bulk, since the base surfactant concentration is 1 CMC, where micelle formation can be expected to be minimal. Furthermore, if micelles of the dye are formed, they can be expected to be self-quenched. This rationale is further supported by the observed symmetry-breaking in soap films which could be monitored via resonance energy transfer, that could only occur if the dyes were transported from one interface of the soap film to the other, i.e. it could not have been observed if a large part of the dyes had been located in the bulk water of the soap film.

Vauthey and co-workers employed SFG to investigate the excited state dynamics of Rhodamine at the dodecane/water interface, and found no difference in the excited state dynamics except the shortening of lifetime due to formation of aggregates, i.e. the familiar effect of self-quenching due to larger concentrations of the dye at the interface¹³. Zare has reported that a Diels-Alder reaction simply does not take place in a microdroplet, as opposed to the bulk, suggesting that not every reaction is slated to benefit from interfacial rate enhancement¹⁴. Ultimately, it becomes important to acknowledge that the picture of interfacial reactivity may be more complicated still, particularly in the context of bimolecular reactions.

At first glance, it may appear that the reactions should become faster due to purely concentration considerations. Yet, as has been recently shown, while there may exist a net field at the interface, the potentials which give rise to the field are dynamic in nature, with large-amplitude fluctuations on an ultra-fast timescale (sub-ps) around the average value of ca. 1 V/nm.¹¹ The impact of these rapidly fluctuating potentials on encounter complexes need be considered, which may, on the whole, average out. For example, while the encounter complex between the surface-bound dye and a bulk quencher may initially be formed with the quencher directed towards the bulk, the encounter complex may undergo random rotational diffusion during its lifetime, such that the electric field becomes randomly oriented relative to the direction of electron transfer. It is also pertinent if the formed products escape into solution or the gas-phase, since this can be thought to substantially impact the overall energetics. To conclude, while no singular reason can be ascertained at this time for observations made in this report, they add to the small, but important counterbalance of studies indicating non-spectacular reactivity at the interface, thus encouraging further questioning.

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